

Equality Education in Prisons: Youth Detention Centre Model

***Rumiari Rumiari**

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8801-9711>

Ach Rasyad

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5518-7149>

Endang Sri Redjeki

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0232-3685>

Abdul Latif Bustami

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5591-7359>

Department of Nonformal Education, Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia

*Corresponding Author: rumiari.2301419@students.um.ac.id

Abstract

Background: Education is a means for humans to grow, according to their inherent abilities and the environment they inhabit, to discover their true identity. The success of education and skills depends on the choice of learning approach, one that is experiential without an emphasis on learning. Education and skills provide opportunities for adolescents and adults in prisons to develop knowledge and skills.

Objective: This research aims to describe the successful implementation of the education and skills necessary for inmates to achieve rehabilitation and reintegration into society.

Methodology: This study employed a qualitative research approach to gather in-depth data through interviews with key informants and observational fieldwork. The study utilised a case study approach, focusing on the Youth Detention Centre model.

Results: This research demonstrates that equality education within the Youth Detention Centre model provides inmates with opportunities to acquire education and skills, thereby enhancing their personal development, improving the quality of life during rehabilitation, and facilitating their reintegration into society upon release.

Conclusion: Educating inmates is a valuable strategy for rehabilitation, ensuring they are smoothly integrated into society.

Unique Contribution: Information from this study could be useful in understanding issues related to the empowerment of less privileged populations.

Key Recommendation: Further studies should be conducted in other locations to facilitate comparison.

Keywords: Equality Education, Youth Detention Centre, Assisted Citizens, Rehabilitation, Community Reintegration

Introduction

Education carried out in correctional institutions is an opportunity and need that is desired by inmates who drop out of school and want to continue their education with the opportunities available. How is equality education for inmates in correctional institutions? Education provides opportunities to learn for those who are left behind due to being school dropouts (Mosiara, 2023). By involving the community in the coaching process, it is hoped that inmates can more easily adapt and reintegrate into society after completing their sentences, and it can also be a solution to increase the effectiveness of education programs in prisons (Darwis, 2020). Learning programs that are "above and beyond the school" can only be organized by school educational institutions and non-school educational institutions through non-formal and informal education programs (Supriyono, 2023).

Non-formal education to overcome school dropouts. The quality of human resources, people's living conditions, and job prospects are all improved by education (Ahmad et al., 2023). To meet the needs of learning citizens identified by the government as needing education, the community organizes non-formal education (Zulkarnain et al., 2024). Communities can achieve national education goals for the equitable distribution and expansion of educational opportunities by utilising equitable education programs, which have been shown to offer a wide range of learning possibilities (Rahma et al., 2021). Ongoing support is essential to prevent relapse and ensure that inmates can function properly in society (Raharni et al., 2020).

Providing equal access to education for all, especially those who cannot pursue formal education pathways, is the main goal of equality education (Alsayed and Omer, 2022). Although teaching at the Special Institute for Child Growth and Development (LPKA) adheres to applicable regulations, these facilities often fall short of facilitating a successful learning process (Argita et al., 2021). The accessibility issue at hand is the delay in receiving education due to limited opportunities, which are often restricted by age and condition, making education inaccessible (Mukholis, 2022). Addressing the social and economic problems faced by equality education students, such as poverty and high dropout rates that affect their motivation and involvement in educational programs, is the goal of these programs (Mulyawan et al., 2020).

Education and skills in Correctional Institutions reduce recidivism rates. Inmates who participated in educational programs had a 32% lower chance of committing repeat offenders than their peers who did not, showing a significant decrease in recidivism rates, the program also contributed to rehabilitation and reduced recidivism rates, as it provided skills that could be used after they were released (Holmes, and Waliczek, 2019). An inmate's desire to recover and reintegrate into society can be strengthened with education and skills (Breuer et al., 2021). Prison education has the power to change the perspective of offenders and lower their risk of committing crimes again. Programs for education and skills development are also important (Monica, 2024). By providing useful skills to offenders, prison technical and vocational training programs seek to reduce recidivism rates (Aripin et al. 2022).

The implementation of equivalence education with one of the YDC model programs. Juvenile detention is critical, and pretrial detention is often the basis of entry for young people (Walker and Herting, 2020). Initiatives to improve the social environment in juvenile detention facilities have also been investigated to improve the general well-being of incarcerated adolescents (Trotter et al., 2022). Although some relevant stakeholders assist YDC in its coaching process, those from the commercial or civil society sectors are more involved than those from other government organisations (Meutia et al., 2021). In addition, understand and create adult education, especially in the prison education environment (Mutsaers, 2023). Offers an important framework for understanding and creating adult education, especially in prison education settings (Conway, 2022). YDC focuses on self-development, training and skills so that inmates can contribute positively to society after completing their sentence. The effectiveness of training is influenced by the behaviour, attitude, knowledge, and skills of the training organiser and the environment of the training activity. The training arrangement and the attitude of the trainer both have an impact on how effective the training is (Rasyad, 2021).

The importance of the YDC model of equality education research provides opportunities for adolescents serving sentences to gain knowledge and skills that are currently marginalised. Through thorough research, effective strategies can be proposed to create a more equitable learning environment. This research can identify barriers to academic success to help develop equality education programs tailored to the needs of the inmates. In addition, it helps to reintegrate them into society, increasing the chances of inmates pursuing further education or employment after release. The purpose of this study is to describe the successful application of the education and skills needed by prisoners for rehabilitation and reintegration into society. The novelty and uniqueness of this study can address the educational gaps faced by youth incarcerated due to poor conditions, uncover tailored strategies that promote equitable education, introduce new methods that actively engage youth in shaping their educational experiences, and consider the comprehensive needs of youth, promoting well-being for reintegration into society.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach. In-depth information was obtained through a qualitative research approach (Sugiyono & Susy, 2022). Qualitative research focuses on actual data, the precise information underlying visible data. Therefore, qualitative research does not emphasise generalisations but rather emphasises meaning. Case studies and other qualitative research often use inductive analysis, which emphasizes meaning from the subject's point of view (Fadli, 2021). By carefully planning the research and adhering to established protocols, case studies can be used to achieve descriptive or explanatory goals (Rustendi, 2023).

This research will shed light on the equality, education, and skills of the YDC model. This type of case study research uses in-depth interview techniques. A case study is the in-depth study of people (it can be a group, organisation, or individual), events, and backgrounds. The purpose of this research is to get an in-depth picture of a case being studied—researchers about programs, events, processes or activities that contain meaning. In the process of selecting informants, the researcher uses a purposive technique, which is that the researcher chooses people who are considered to know the problem being researched.

During the researcher's face-to-face interview with the informant to collect data, the informant asks questions about the outline of the guidelines that have been created beforehand. To understand the context and significance of the data collected, direct communication with the research subject is needed (Amin, 2022). Interviews are conducted by researchers for 120 minutes for each informant until the information needed by the researcher is met and he can answer the research focus that the researcher has determined. The researcher here only acts as an observer, so the presence of the researcher in this study is included in the passive participatory category so that he will know and get a clear picture of what is observed. The implementation of observation was carried out in the following steps: (1) starting activities before entering the field, the researcher conducted a pre-field service at the LAPAS as the location for the implementation of YDC-based equality education learning to obtain an overview; (2) the researcher is present to collect data about the prospective informant who will be interviewed, (3) the researcher is also present to look for documents that are considered necessary as additional data.

Results And Discussion

Results

Based on the focus of the problem is "Equality Education in Prison: Model Youth Detention Center (YDC) in Class II B Correctional Institution Singkawang" which includes: (1) the implementation of the Youth Detention Center (YDC) in non-formal education in Class II B Singkawang Correctional Institution, (2) functional equality program package B for students in Class II B Singkawang Correctional Institution, (3) functional equality learning package B for students in Singkawang Class II B Correctional Institution, (3) functional equality learning package B for students in Singkawang. Class II B Correctional Institution Singkawang.

1. Implementation of Youth Detention Center (YDC) in Non-formal Education in Class II B Singkawang Correctional Institution

Implementing juvenile detention centers in prisons is a complex task that requires careful consideration and planning by creating a safe and supportive environment within the prison system. Meanwhile, the RIS informant explained the important steps for the implementation of YDC in prisons as follows:

Yes, (1) before implementing a juvenile detention center in prison, it is important to conduct a thorough needs assessment to understand the specific requirements of young offenders. This assessment should take into account factors such as age, education, mental health, and the nature of their offense. By understanding the unique needs of young offenders, we can tailor programs and services to effectively address their challenges. (2) Education and skills programs, namely, one of the main objectives of the Child Detention Center is to provide educational and training opportunities for young offenders. We, implementing on-site schools or partnering with educational institutions, can help ensure that young offenders continue their education while incarcerated. In addition, Sir, we offer skills training programs that can equip them with valuable skills that enhance their employability after release. (RIS.W2.F1.SF.1)

Furthermore, JUN conveyed the following steps to implement YDC in education and skills:

Yes, sir, there is also family and community involvement, which is combining family and community involvement initiatives is very important for the successful implementation of

juvenile detention centers in prisons. We set regular visitation schedules, and community reintegration programs can help young inmates gain meaningful support outside of detention centers. Then, Sir, the continuous monitoring and evaluation of child detention home programs and services are essential to ensure their effectiveness. Regular assessments should be conducted to measure the impact of implemented initiatives and identify areas for improvement. (JUN. W3. F1. SF.1)

The Education Program at YDC is an important component of the rehabilitation process for incarcerated adolescents by improving the quality of programs in prisons that are more meaningful for the needs of students who are learning to return to society.

Figure 1. Skill learning process

2. Functional Equivalency Program Package B for Students at Class II B Singkawang Penitentiary

a. Identification of Program Needs

Identifying the need for skills programs in prisons. By identifying these needs, a comprehensive program that includes education, technical skills, and personal development can be designed to address rehabilitation. Other community-based social empowerment programs can support better personalities through religion. The researchers documented the identification of the needs of inmates or study inmates in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The program needs identification activities

This was also conveyed by RIS regarding the needs of the program for students while at YDC as follows:

Rehabilitation activities in prisons include a holistic approach, integrating various medical, social, and psychological aspects to support inmates in the process of recovery and reintegration into society. With the implementation of the right

program and adequate support, it is hoped that inmates can transform into productive individuals and contribute positively to society after completing their sentences.(RIS.W2.F1.SF.1)

By tailoring skills programs to meet these needs, authorities can contribute significantly to reducing recidivism rates and creating opportunities for successful reintegration. The HID informant provided answers related to the question "Are the learning materials by the needs of students?" HID explained, "Yes, sir, the material I conveyed was adjusted to the condition of the students as in the learning module".

b. Program Planning

Prison skills and educational program planning are important components of the rehabilitation process for inmates. RIS says about skills and educational program planning, as follows:

Currently, in the prison that I lead, there are several educational programs through Education and Skills development, one of which is the functional equality education package B. Determining the planning of skills education programs gives students the freedom to choose needs that suit their desires and interests that can equip them with the ability to work when they are released. (RIS. W1. F1. SF2)

One of the key aspects of effective program planning in prison is understanding the needs of learners. It involves conducting a thorough assessment to identify gaps in skills and interests among learners. JUN said during the interview as follows:

Yes, sir. We have plans to nurture students in this Education program. We will carry out planning according to the same schedule as PKBM, which provides teaching staff. So far, what we have done with PKBM is in the development of equality education, skills education and community education. We at Pak collect data on the needs of individual learners and provide direction on the importance of skills to prepare for the future when they are free and can rely on economic income. (JUN. W2. F1. SF2)

c. Program Implementation

The implementation of skills and education programs in prison facilities is an important and often overlooked aspect of rehabilitation. RIS also said that the implementation of programs in prisons in the YDC program is as follows;

We were able to implement some of the designs of these programs to address the unique challenges faced by youth in prison settings, including resource constraints, rehabilitation needs, and educational care. One example of an important program is the implementation of education and skills programs. The program provides knowledge of the rights and obligations of citizens, which is essential for the social reintegration of prisoners after they have completed their sentences. The implementation of programs in correctional institutions (prisons) is an important aspect of prison rehabilitation, which aims to prepare them to return to society with the necessary skills and knowledge. (RIS. W2. F1. SF2)

Furthermore, the HID informant provided an explanation related to the implementation of the equality education program package B and skills for students as follows:

What I give to students is a package B learning activity, after which they are given skills according to their needs that are their choice that is easy to prepare when they

are free. Learning implementation activities are carried out according to the schedule and needs. They were very enthusiastic about participating in this program together, and learning implementation activities were carried out according to the schedule and needs. They are very enthusiastic about participating in this program together. This activity can certainly be followed by all students of package B, then accompanied by officers who also help with the implementation of learning and skills. (HID. W5. F.SF.2)

The results showed that inmates who attended vocational education and training programs while in prison were less likely to re-offend after release. Researchers document the implementation of the skills of inmates or students in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Implementation of student learning skills

d. Program Evaluation

The implementation of skills and education programs in the prison environment is an interesting course. The JUN informant also emphasized how to evaluate the program that has been implemented and the continuation of the program as follows:

Yes, sir, we have completed each program, and then we evaluate the program related to the shortcomings and advantages. From several programs that we have implemented, we submit a report to the head of the prison on the extent of the results and impact of the programs that we have carried out. Of course, we involve several other employees related to support and tutors as well as PKBM managers as our partners, sir. Prison skills program evaluations have several important objectives. That is, providing valuable insights into the impact of these programs on inmates. By assessing the effectiveness of the skills training provided, the authority can make data-driven decisions about continuing, expanding, or modifying the program. (JUN. W2. F1. SF3)

Information from RIS related to program evaluation during the interview led to the success or failure of the guidance implemented through the Youth Detention Center at the Class II B Singkawang Correctional Institution as follows:

The results of program evaluations in correctional institutions (prisons) are an important aspect in understanding the effectiveness of various rehabilitation programs designed to reduce the rate of reoffending and increase the reintegration of inmates into society. Systematic evaluations not only provide insight into the strengths and weaknesses of the program but also aid in making better policy

decisions and improving outcomes for individuals involved in the justice system. One of the main focuses of program evaluation in prisons is skills education and training. In addition, some emphasize the importance of community-based interventions, such as training programs, which not only provide practical skills but also enhance the social and cultural capital of inmates with inmate learning. (RIS. W2. F1. SF2)

3. Functional Equivalency Learning Package B for Students in Class II B Singkawang Prison

a. Selecting Learning Methods and Media

HID, when interviewed, said that regarding the determination of learning methods through YDC, as follows;

Yes, sir, I have already determined what method I use every time I teach. Of course, before teaching, I prepare equipment or materials for teaching. I arrange everything in the Learning Implementation Plan or RPP. In it, I display learning methods by the essence of the material in the subject. (HID. W6. F1. SF3)

AMI, when interviewed about the learning media used during learning in Correctional Institutions, said the following:

I consider the availability of diverse learning materials and resources as very important. Printed materials, such as textbooks, workbooks, and instructional books, remain the foundation of prison education, especially for developing basic skills in reading, writing, and arithmetic. (AMI. W7. F1. SF3)

b. Learning Strategies in Correctional Institutions

When it comes to implementing effective learning strategies for incarcerated individuals, it's important to tailor the approach. HID informant explains the question of how do you implement the learning process through YDC? As follows:

The learning process that I do starts from asking about health news, motivating to learn, and positive encouragement for them during the learning process. In addition, learning process activities are carried out, reading until they ask questions. Yes, sir. In learning activities with YDC, we have prepared what are the steps so that I and other tutors can easily deliver the material. Yes, sir, they learn to interact with each other in one study group. Which study group is by the learning conditions and the material presented? With the learning process activities through the YDC model, I feel happy and helped. Previously, learning activities were not carried out, considering the absence of an educational program. Helping in learning with the YDC model, I and my friends gained new knowledge. (HID. W5. F.SF.3)

The researcher then collected data by collecting documents in the form of pictures showing tutors in learning strategies through Figure 4:

Figure 4. Learning of equivalent education package B

c. Evaluation of Learning Process Outcomes

Education is a powerful tool that can help individuals transform their lives and create new opportunities.

HID said regarding the question "Does the tutor evaluate the learning process?" according to HID, the learning evaluation is of course Yes, sir, there is. Evaluation is given after students have finished receiving learning from each learning topic, then we collect and analyze each grade, as a form of achievement after learning," replied the informant during the interview. The RIS informant explained the importance of conducting learning evaluations for students as follows:

Evaluation of the outcomes of the learning process in prison is essential to enable prison administrators and tutors to assess the impact of educational programs on the lives of incarcerated students. Through evaluation, it becomes possible to measure the effectiveness of various educational initiatives and identify areas that need improvement. This information can then be used to refine educational programs and ensure that they meet the needs of incarcerated populations. In addition, evaluating the outcomes of the learning process in prison provides valuable data for assessing the long-term outcomes of education on recidivism rates. (RIS. W8. F1. SF2)

The JUN informant explained regarding the evaluation of learning outcomes given to students at the class II B Singkawang penitentiary that:

Evaluation of the learning process in prisons is essential to understand its effectiveness and impact on prisoner rehabilitation. Through systematic assessment, we can measure how educational programs contribute to skills development, behavior modification, and overall readiness for reintegration into society. Evaluating learning outcomes in a prison environment can be challenging due to factors such as different levels of inmate motivation, the influence of external social conditions, and institutional limitations. Recognizing these challenges is essential to creating a realistic evaluation framework in the Class II B Singkawang Correctional Institution. (JUN. W3. F1. SF2)

Discussion

The implementation of YDC provides support to overcome programme obstacles in achieving success in prisons. The results of the research findings in the field show that the YDC implementation program has several components, as follows: (1) education and skills. The benefits are not only felt by individuals, as working ex-criminals have less chance of committing crimes again, thus contributing to public safety. Knowledge through skills and vocational training in prisons is focused on providing practical and job-specific skills. Individuals who participate in educational programs while in prison are less likely to re-offend after release. By acquiring new skills and knowledge, inmates will be better prepared to reintegrate into society constructively, thereby reducing the burden on the criminal justice system and contributing to overall public

safety. (2) social empowerment. Social empowerment is done with family support and religious support, which can benefit individuals and also contribute to their personal development. Empowering individuals and giving them a second chance to live a fulfilling life, breaking the cycle of criminal behaviour. Behaviour in prison encompasses a variety of strategies aimed at addressing and changing inmate behaviour patterns. These interventions are designed to encourage positive behaviour change, reduce recidivism, and ultimately contribute to the successful reintegration of individuals into society after release. (3) Vocational training. This sense of hope can be transformational, motivating individuals to make constructive changes in their lives. In addition, the structure and routines offered by training programs often provide a sense of normalcy, reducing the likelihood of engaging in illicit activities in prison. By offering academic and vocational courses, inmates are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to pursue alternative paths upon release.

The findings are in line with the concept ("The Impact of Court Decisions on Juvenile Recidivism Offenders", 2024), which suggests that adolescents who receive rehabilitation interventions are significantly less likely to re-offend compared to those who experience traditional incarceration. This means that building rehabilitation requires the implementation of the YDC program through education and skills. In addition, it is also based on the findings of a previous research conducted (Jia et al., 2021) entitled Economic evaluation of Thai youth vocational training centres. Emphasising the importance of skill development and education in improving the quality of life of adolescents at risk of recidivism. Providing vocational education in juvenile detention centres can significantly improve the employability of young offenders, thereby reducing the likelihood of reoffending. This is in line with the findings of researchers conducted by Carey (2024), vocational training opportunities in detention centres can help reduce recidivism rates and provide valuable skills for detained adolescents. The results of the study show that the meaning of functional equality in learning package B based on YDC is very diverse and unique. This opinion can be concluded that citizens learn equality and skills education is an opportunity to acquire learning knowledge and improve the quality of life for the better, and not repeat crimes when returning to society. From the focus of the problem of how functional equity learning is interpreted, the learning provided to inmates or students at YDC starts from learning, such as learning in school, by providing materials according to design (Lawrence, 2022).

The content of the material can certainly provide support for the needs of inmates, which are implemented functionally after participating in the learning process. It is proven that inmates can obtain education and training skills according to their needs and job opportunities. This is in line with the Andragogy Theory, developed by Malcolm Knowles (Edwards-Fapohunda, 2024), which emphasizes that adults learn differently from children, with a focus on life experiences, motivations, and the need to control their learning process. In the prison context, the application of andragogy principles can help create a more inclusive and empowering learning environment for inmates. The Theory of Transformational Learning, developed by Jack Mezirow, emphasizes the importance of experience and reflection in the learning process. In the context of prison education, transformational learning can help inmates change their perspective on themselves and their environment. According to Keen and Woods in Conway (2024), prison education can create an "activation event" that encourages inmates to reflect on their life experiences and develop new understandings. It is also written by Khan et al. (2023), which emphasizes the economic, social,

and moral imperatives to increase lifelong learning opportunities for offenders. Based on the discussion with theory, the definition of functional equality learning package B based on YDC for students is: (1) with equality education that provides opportunities for prisoners to obtain the right to learn and continue their education; (2) by acquiring skills to increase employment opportunities upon returning to society; (3) education and functional equality skills to improve a person's personality so that they do not repeat criminal acts; (4) provide meaningful new life experiences in participating in learning in prison; (5) improve rehabilitation goals and reduce recidivism rates.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research and the discussion of the results, in general, it can be concluded that the implementation of the Youth Detention Center (YDC) is as follows (1) the existence of YDC provides education and supervision that synergistically between LAPAS and BAPAS in preparing prisoners to be able to reintegrate into society, crime prevention, empowerment, education and reintegration into society; (2) provide more targeted educational and skills program services during rehabilitation; (3) prepare inmates who have good personalities and improve the quality of education and skills programs. This is evidenced by the implementation of the Youth Detention House (YDC) as a detention place to provide education and skills programs for inmates to adolescents in rehabilitation to improve their quality of life after they return to society. YDC also serves as a place to reduce risky behaviors among adolescents and a program to restore better personal behavior.

References

- Ahmad, et al., (2023). Tren perkembangan pendidikan non-formal. *Jurnal Pendidikan (Teori Dan Praktik)*, 7(2), 76-82. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jp.v7n2.p76-82>
- Argita, A., Gunawan, C., Risnawati, R., Syahrini, S., & Nasir, N. (2021). Manajemen pembelajaran: program belajar anak binaan di lapas anak kota kendar. *Journal of Education and Teaching (Jet)*, 2(2), 121-128. <https://doi.org/10.51454/jet.v2i2.113>
- Breuer, E., Rémond, M., Lighton, S., Passalacqua, J., Galouzis, J., Stewart, K., ... & Sullivan, E. (2021). *The needs and experiences of mothers while in prison and post-release: a rapid review and thematic synthesis*. *Health & Justice*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40352-021-00153-7>
- Conway, P. (2022). *Andragogy in prison: higher education in prison and the tenets of adult education*. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 72(4), 361-379. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07417136221100481>
- Edwards-Fapohunda, D. M. O. (2024). The role of adult learning and education in community development: A case study of New York. *Iconic Research And Engineering Journals*, 8(1), 437-454.
- Fadli, M. (2021). Memahami desain metode penelitian kualitatif. *Humanika*, 21(1), 33-54. <https://doi.org/10.21831/hum.v21i1.38075>
- Holmes, M. and Waliczek, T. (2019). *The effect of horticultural community service programs on recidivism*. *Horttechnology*, 29(4), 490-495. <https://doi.org/10.21273/horttech04282-19>
- Knowles, M., et al, (2005). *Adult Learner*, Elsevier, UK

- Khan, M. I., Nisar, A., & Kanwell, S. (2023). From Punishment to Progress: The Legal Evolution of Criminal Rehabilitation. *Pakistan JL Analysis & Wisdom*, 2, 556
- Lawrence, B. H. (2022). “*Education Not Protection*” *Student Activism on Western North Carolina Campuses, 1960s and 1970s*. Western Carolina University
- Mosiara, S.(2023). Menjelajahi peran pendidikan dalam mempromosikan keadilan sosial di negara-negara sub-Sahara. *IJHSS*, 1(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.47941/ijhss.1428>
- Meutia, I. F., Sujadmiko, B., Putri, D. E., & Kurniawan, D.(2021). *The Idea of Youth Detention Center: Education Program and Policy*. *J. Legal Ethical & Regul. Issues*, 24, 1
- Monica, M.(2024). *The future of rehabilitation: AI and the transformation of education in prisons*. *Eat*. <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i2.2996>
- Mutsaers, P.(2023). *Decolonising youth justice, rethinking childhood: Caribbean counterstories in detention*. *Youth Justice*, 14732254231156845
- Rasyad, (2021). Model Tata Kelola Pelatihan Yang Efektif Berbasis Pendekatan Fleksibilitas, Kolaboratif, Dan Partisipatif
- Rustendi, T. (2023). Pendekatan kuantitatif dalam studi kasus pada penelitian bidang akuntansi. *Jurnal Akuntansi*, 17(1), 24-37. <https://doi.org/10.37058/jak.v17i1.6736>
- Supriyono, S.,(2023). Pendidikan non formal dan Pendidikan Masyarakat. Baskara Media, Malang.
- Trotter, C., Evans, P., & Powers, T.(2022). *Improving social climate in youth detention*. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 68(4), 353-369. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624x221102852>
- Walker, S. and Herting, J. (2020). *The impact of pretrial juvenile detention on 12-month recidivism: a matched comparison study*. *Crime & Delinquency*, 66(13-14), 1865-1887. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011128720926115>
- Zulkarnain, et al.,(2024). Membangun Masyarakat Melalui Pendidikan Luar Sekolah. *Media Pendidikan Plus2*, Malang.